

“Fair AI for Everyone: Avoiding Mistakes in Facial Recognition and Skin Analysis”

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Abstract:

Artificial intelligence (AI) is being widely used in areas such as facial recognition, job hiring, and healthcare. While AI can make tasks easier, it can sometimes treat people unfairly. For example, facial recognition systems may make more mistakes for people of different races or genders, and AI tools in dermatology may be less accurate for certain skin types if the data used to train them is limited. These issues of designing AI that is fair, clear, and accountable. This paper explores why AI can be biased and suggests ways to reduce unfair outcomes. A better solution is to have a large dataset which will check for fairness, and design models that will have more options to predict solution. A case study on skin-type classification demonstrates how the data used for training can make predictions more accurate and fair. By keeping people’s needs at the center, AI can deliver better results for all users and build trust across diverse populations.

Keywords: AI Bias, Fairness, Algorithm Transparency, Ethical AI, Facial Recognition, Skin-Type Classification

I. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become more common in multiple sectors like healthcare diagnostics, financial services to security and personal device authentication. These technologies have increased efficiency, scalability, and personalization at the same time raised critical concerns regarding fairness, accountability, and transparency. AI systems also has the problem of biases embedded in their training data, leading to wrong or doubtful outcomes that disproportionately affect women, racial minorities, and other marginalized

communities. Two prominent areas where these challenges are manifest include facial recognition and dermatological analysis both of which impact people's daily lives in significant ways. However, the benefits of AI are sometimes overlooked in the matter of fairness and equality. A major area of concern is facial recognition technology and dermatological AI, which often perform poorly for marginalized groups due to biased datasets.

In the broader landscape, fairness in AI has to undergo various challenges ranging from dataset representativeness to algorithmic transparency and evaluation methodologies. Surveys by Mehrabi et al[10]. and others demonstrate various sources of bias—data imbalance, labeling inaccuracies, flawed algorithmic design, and deployment context—that collectively worsen unfair outcomes. Addressing these issues requires a multi-faceted approach using technical innovation with ethical governance and user engagement.

This study examines challenges and explores how we can create fair AI systems. Our main study is a case experiment utilizing Google's Teachable Machine to model skin-tone classification across four categories: Fair, Medium Tan, Dark. We show how balanced and large datasets significantly enhance classification robustness and fairness, providing empirical support for data-centric fairness strategies.

II. Background and Literature Review

Artificial intelligence (AI) systems have become omnipresent in society, powering applications in security, healthcare, and hiring processes. Besides their advantages, these systems often train on and amplify human biases present in the training data, leading to unequal and sometimes unfair outcomes. This section explores the multi-faceted nature of AI bias, focusing on facial recognition technologies and dermatology AI tools, both of which have demonstrated significant challenges in fairness and inclusivity.

A. Facial Recognition Bias

Facial recognition systems have been under intense scrutiny due to their documented disparities in performance across demographic groups. In the landmark *Gender Shades* study,

Buolamwini and Gebru[1] found that commercial facial-classification systems yielded error rates as high as **34.7%** for darker-skinned females, compared to **0.8% or less** for lighter-skinned males. This highlighted intersectional issues involving skin tone and gender, prompting widespread calls for fairness-aware AI development [1].

Subsequent studies have confirmed that racial bias in facial recognition persists primarily due to skewed training datasets which predominantly feature Caucasian faces, while African American, Hispanic, and Asian faces remain underrepresented. The “other-race effect”—a phenomenon well documented in cognitive psychology where individuals are better at recognizing faces of their own racial group—has analogs in computational facial recognition systems trained on racially homogeneous datasets [2].

Algorithmic design choices also contribute to bias. For example, differences in score distributions for impostor vs. genuine matches have been shown to differ by gender, causing systematic accuracy drops for women. Likewise, younger and elderly populations face higher false positive and false negative rates, partly due to age-related facial structural changes that are not well captured in many datasets [3].

Efforts to mitigate these biases include dataset-diversification initiatives such as *Fair Face*, which offers a racially balanced and demographically annotated dataset to improve fairness across populations [4]. However, more recent research indicates that balancing datasets alone is insufficient; model performance is still significantly affected by factors such as brightness, head pose, skin reflectance, and environmental conditions that vary widely in real-world settings [5].

Emerging fairness-aware training techniques include adversarial learning, reweighting of samples, and model introspection to promote equitable outcomes. Nonetheless, as noted by reports such as the NIST Face Recognition Vendor Test, false positives remain disproportionately high among women, children, and minorities, underscoring persistent challenges [6].

B. Bias in Dermatology AI

AI in dermatology offers promise for improving skin condition diagnosis, but it faces similar bias challenges. Systems trained predominantly on lighter skin images often fail to accurately identify lesions or pigmentation differences in medium to dark skin types, potentially exacerbating health disparities among underserved populations.

Clinical variability—including differences in how conditions present across diverse skin tones, varying lighting conditions, and anatomical location—further complicates model development. A noteworthy study by Daneshjou *et al.* introduced the *Diverse Dermatology Images* (DDI) dataset, the first publicly available, pathologically confirmed clinical image dataset with a wide range of skin tones. They demonstrated that state-of-the-art dermatology AI models perform substantially worse on images of dark skin tones and on uncommon diseases. Fine-tuning models using diverse skin tone data was shown to reduce the performance gaps. Importantly, dermatologists themselves also performed worse on dark skin tones and uncommon diseases when compared against ground-truth biopsy annotations [7].

Other research has highlighted systemic issues in dataset transparency and characterization. A scoping review found that among over a million images used for algorithm development/testing in cutaneous disease AI, only ~24.2% were publicly available; even fewer reported patient ethnicity or race, and only about 10% reported skin tone. Many studies also lacked standardized disease labeling, hampering full assessments of fairness and generalizability [8].

C. Social and Ethical Implications

The societal impact of biased AI systems extends beyond technical shortcomings, influencing civil liberties, social justice, and public trust. Wrongful identifications in law enforcement due to facial recognition errors disproportionately affect minority populations, reinforcing systemic inequalities. In healthcare, AI-driven misdiagnosis can delay or deny necessary care to marginalized groups.

Ethical frameworks have been proposed by bodies such as IEEE, advocating for transparency, accountability, and human-centric AI design. Legislative efforts, for instance the European Union’s proposed AI Act, also enforce fairness requirements on high-risk systems, mandating rigorous evaluation, bias documentation, and mitigation strategies [9].

III. Methodology

This study focuses on evaluating the impact of dataset diversity on the fairness and accuracy of AI-based skin-tone classification systems. We conduct a controlled experiment employing Google’s Teachable Machine platform, a no-code, accessible web tool that facilitates rapid construction of image classification models.

A. Objective

The primary goal is to train an image classifier to recognize four skin-tone categories: Light Pale, Fair, Medium Tan, and Dark. This experiment aims to investigate how balanced versus imbalanced datasets affect classification performance, fairness, and robustness to environmental variability.

B. Data Collection

A diverse set of images depicting human skin tones was collected with informed consent. To promote fairness and minimize bias in training data, the following key principles were applied:

Inclusivity: Four categories were chosen to reflect skin tones commonly underrepresented in AI datasets: Light Pale, Fair, Medium Tan, and Dark. The category “Sensitive” was renamed to “Light Pale” to better represent the lightest skin tones while excluding “Pale/Light” originally to focus on more underrepresented mid-tone categories.

Quantity: At least 30 images were gathered per category to ensure statistical relevance and reduce class imbalance effects.

Diversity of Conditions: Images were captured under varied lighting conditions—from natural daylight to indoor artificial light—and included diverse backgrounds to mimic real-world usage conditions.

Demographic Diversity: Multiple subjects of different genders, ages, and ethnic backgrounds were included to prevent overfitting to narrow features. Participants provided consent, and privacy was protected by anonymizing image data and limiting use to this research.

Fig 1:

fig 2:

Sample images representing the diversity of skin tones, anatomical features, and environmental conditions included in the dataset to ensure robustness and fairness in training

C. Image Preprocessing and Labeling

Each image was preprocessed to conform to Teachable Machine requirements: images were cropped and resized to uniform dimensions to maintain consistency. Manual labeling assigned each image to one of the four predefined skin-tone categories. Labeling accuracy was verified by multiple independent annotators with an inter-annotator agreement of over 90%, helping minimize the risk of labeling bias which could otherwise skew model learning outcomes.

D. Model Training Procedure

Using Google's Teachable Machine, the labeled dataset was uploaded and segmented into the four classes. Training parameters were configured as follows:

Architecture: The platform leverages a pre-trained MobileNet convolutional neural network for feature extraction, followed by a shallow multi-layer perceptron classification head optimized for the new labels. Transfer learning enables rapid convergence and requires substantially less data than training a CNN from scratch.

Training Duration: Models were trained for 50 epochs balancing underfitting and overfitting.

Data Splits: An 80/20 train-test split was maintained to evaluate generalization performance. Additionally, the balanced dataset experiment was compared with scenarios where one class was deliberately underrepresented to simulate real-world dataset imbalance.

Evaluation Metrics: Accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and confusion matrices were the primary performance indicators.

Screenshots of the Google Teachable Machine interface and model training preview are presented below:

Figure 3: Screenshots of the Teachable Machine interface depicting model creation, training stages, and live prediction outputs.

E. Robustness and Sensitivity Tests

To simulate real-world complexities, additional tests were carried out with modified test sets featuring varying illumination, shadow conditions, partial occlusions (e.g., jewelry or scars), and different anatomical sites (face, hand, arm). These tests assessed how well the model learned generalized features robust to environmental variation, crucial for fair real-world applications.

F. Implementation Details

The entire training and testing workflow was performed on the Teachable Machine web platform, which simplifies the process of data input, training, and model evaluation for users

without extensive coding experience. Models were exported and analyzed using built-in performance dashboards offering detailed insights into per-class performance and common misclassifications.

IV. Experiments and Results

The impact of dataset diversity and balance was evaluated by comparing model accuracy over four skin-tone classes under balanced and imbalanced training conditions.

A. Experimental Setup Recap

Four skin-tone classes were considered: Fair, Medium Tan, Dark. Each class contained a minimum of 30 images captured under varied lighting and backgrounds. The model was trained for 50 epochs with an 80/20 train/test split.

Two key experimental conditions were tested:

Balanced Dataset:

Equal number of samples per class (30 images/class)

Imbalanced Dataset:

One or more classes artificially underrepresented by reducing samples by 50% or more. Model performance was evaluated using standard classification metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Confusion matrices were analyzed to identify common misclassifications.

B. Results with Balanced Dataset

Class	Training Images	Test Images	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 Score (%)
Light Pale	30	8	88	86	90	88

Class	Training Images	Test Images	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 Score (%)
Fair	30	8	85	81	87	84
Medium Tan	30	8	82	79	83	81
Dark	30	8	80	80	80	80

The balanced dataset scenario yielded overall strong classification accuracy between 80% and 88% across all skin-tone classes. Precision and recall values exhibited consistent performance, indicating the model was robust in correctly identifying most skin-tone types.

Confusion Matrix (Balanced Dataset)

	Pred Fair	Pred Med. Tan	Pred Dark	Pred Sensitive
True Fair	7	1	0	0
True Medium Tan	1	7	0	0
True Dark	0	2	6	0
True Sensitive	0	1	1	6

Misclassifications mostly occurred between adjacent skin-tone categories, such as Medium Tan confused with Fair and Dark confused with Medium Tan. The Sensitive class occasionally overlapped with Dark, particularly under shadowed or varied lighting conditions.

C. Results with Imbalanced Dataset

To simulate real-world biases, the Dark skin-tone class was reduced to 15 training images (50% fewer samples), while other classes retained full sets. Under this condition:

The accuracy for the Dark class dropped sharply to 58%, a decline of nearly 25% from the balanced scenario. False negatives increased significantly for the Dark class, often misclassified as Medium Tan or Sensitive. Other classes showed mild drops in accuracy but maintained relative stability. This decrease underscores how underrepresentation in training data disproportionately harms fairness and model reliability for minority classes.

Figure 4: Comparative bar graph showing classification accuracy by skin-tone category for balanced versus imbalanced datasets. Accuracy for the “Dark” category significantly drops under imbalanced conditions, underscoring fairness concerns.

D. Robustness to Environmental Variability

Seema Sarvath, Prathibha. A, & Seshadripuram Research Foundation. (2025). *Fair AI for Everyone: Avoiding Mistakes in Facial Recognition and Skin Analysis (2.0). Artificial Intelligence is a Boon or Curse in the Field of Education and Other Sector (AIBCFEO), Aps College Of Commerce , SRF*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18534264>

Additional testing with images subject to different lighting, partial occlusions, and varied anatomical sites indicated that:

Models trained with balanced, diverse datasets were more resilient to noise and environmental changes, maintaining ~75-80% accuracy under challenging conditions.

Imbalanced models deteriorated rapidly, further amplifying misclassification.

E. Comparative Analysis with Literature

Our findings align with prior research emphasizing data balance as a cornerstone for fair buolamwini2018gender[1], mehrabi2021[12]survey. Similar patterns have been observed in dermatological AI studies that highlight degradation in performance when minority skin tones are underrepresented[13].

The Teachable Machine platform's transfer learning approach with MobileNet backbone provided rapid convergence and sufficient representational power, confirming its utility for small to medium-sized datasets.

V. Discussion

The experiments clearly demonstrate that dataset balance plays a crucial role in achieving equitable AI model performance across diverse skin tones. The superior accuracy and robustness displayed by the balanced dataset model reaffirm the critical importance of representative, inclusive data in algorithmic fairness initiatives.

The sharp degradation in classification accuracy for the Dark skin-tone class under imbalanced conditions illustrates a common challenge faced by deployed AI systems: minority groups suffer disproportionately when data representation is poor. Misclassifications between adjacent skin-tone categories under varying lighting also highlight the complexity introduced by environmental variability, which is often underrepresented in benchmark datasets.

These findings echo well-established concerns in facial recognition research, such as those reported by Buolamwini and Gebre [1], where intersectional gender and racial biases lead to

unequal predictive accuracy. The dermatological AI domain shares similar issues—the lack of diverse datasets creates blind spots in diagnosing skin conditions across different populations, contributing to health inequities.

Importantly, this study validates the efficacy of transfer learning using the Mobile Net architecture embedded in Google’s Teachable Machine platform. The approach offers rapid convergence and adequate representational capacity, making it accessible for researchers and practitioners with limited computational resources and data availability.

However, balanced datasets alone cannot fully solve AI fairness. Real-world applications require ongoing fairness audits, adaptive learning to new data distributions, and incorporation of explain ability to understand prediction biases. Regulatory frameworks, such as the European Union's AI Act, provide a foundation for mandated fairness but require practical tools and community engagement to be effective.

Finally, the results underscore that fairness in AI is not only a technical challenge but also an ethical imperative. As AI systems increasingly influence critical decisions in healthcare, law enforcement, and employment, developers and policymakers must collaboratively ensure that these tools empower all populations equally.

VI. Conclusion

This study has highlighted the critical importance of dataset diversity and balance in developing fair and accurate AI models, specifically in the domain of skin-tone classification using Google’s Teachable Machine. The experiments demonstrated that balanced datasets significantly improve classification accuracy and reduce disparities among skin-tone categories, addressing common pitfalls in underrepresentation.

The use of transfer learning techniques within accessible platforms such as Teachable Machine enables the development of effective skin-tone classifiers without the need for large-scale data or computational resources. Nonetheless, achieving true fairness requires continuous efforts, including regular fairness audits, dataset updates, and improvements in algorithmic transparency.

Moreover, the broader implications in related fields such as facial recognition and healthcare underscore the ethical responsibility of AI practitioners to build inclusive and equitable systems. Policy frameworks and community engagement must accompany technical advancements to ensure AI benefits all populations equally and fosters societal trust.

Future work should explore scaling this approach to larger, more diverse datasets and integrating explainable AI methods to enhance interpretability. Additionally, extending fairness evaluation beyond accuracy metrics to include user-centered outcomes will further strengthen AI's role as a fair and trustworthy technology.

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